

Microfluidic chip-based platform towards replacing the in vivo rodent calvarial critical-size defect model (Izp-2024/1-0509)

Version 1

Description

The Data Management Plan (DMP) is prepared in the framework of the Latvian Council of Science Fundamental and Applied Research project No. Izp-2024/1-0509 "Microfluidic chip-based platform towards replacing the in vivo rodent calvarial critical-size defect model", 01.01.2025-31.12.2027. Project is led by Ph.D. Jana Vecstaudza. The project is implemented in Institute of Biomaterials and Bioengineering, Riga Technical University and Institute of Solid State Physics, University of Latvia. The DMP contains descriptions of three datasets related to Work Packages of the Project. The DMP will be updated during the implementation of the Project at least annually.

Summary of the Project: The growing interest in using biomaterials for bone injury treatment drives the development of new biomaterials, leading to the increased use of costly and ethically complex in vivo animal tests to assess their efficacy for bone regeneration. Therefore, microfluidic chip-based platforms that can accurately mimic in vivo responses to biomaterials in vitro and vice versa are urgently needed. This project addresses the need by combining expertise in microfluidic devices, biomaterials, in vitro tools, and molecular biology to develop a new microfluidics chip-based platform for preclinical in vitro assessment of calcium phosphate-based biomaterials for bone tissue regeneration. Main aims of the project are: 1) design and fabrication of new microfluidic chip for incorporation of bone-like biomaterials, 2) fabrication of calcium phosphate enclosed bone-on-chip and in vitro studies thereof, and 3) correlation studies of calcium phosphate-based biomaterial and cell response in vitro in the chip with existing data from in vivo calvaria critical-size defect rodent model. Implementation of the project will contribute to Latvia's Smart Specialization Strategies for Research and Innovation "Smart

materials, technologies and engineering systems” and promote the overall development of the Latvian economy and biomaterial research and development for healthcare.

Funder

Latvian Council of Science

Grant

Microfluidic chip-based platform towards replacing the in vivo rodent calvarial critical-size defect model (Izp-2024/1-0509)

Researchers

Jana Vecstaudza (0000-0002-1864-1274), Kristaps Klavins (0000-0001-9577-9990), Roberts Rimša (0000-0002-8915-5361)

Organizations

Riga Technical University

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: [Microfluidic chip-based platform towards replacing the in vivo rodent calvarial critical-size defect model \(Izp-2024/1-0509\)](#)

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Researchers:

[Jana Vecstaudza \(0000-0002-1864-1274\)](#)

Kristaps Klavins (0000-0001-9577-9990)

Roberts Rimša (0000-0002-8915-5361)

Organizations:

Riga Technical University

Contact: Vecstaudza Jana (jana.vecstaudza@rtu.lv)

2. Funding

Funding organizations: Latvian Council of Science

Grants: Microfluidic chip-based platform towards replacing the in vivo rodent calvarial critical-size defect model (Izp-2024/1-0509)

Project:

3. License

License: CC-BY-4.0

Access Rights: Public

Publication Date: 2025-03-31

4. Templates

Descriptions

WP2: Fabrication and validation of bone-on-chip with biomaterials and cells

This dataset will include all relevant data planned for publication under the framework of the Project's Work Package 2. Data within the Work Package 2 will be obtained from XRD, FT-IR, SEM, microCT, optical microscopy and mass spectrometry measurements.

Template: LCS FARP

Data Management Plan | Microfluidic chip-based platform towards replacing the in vivo rodent calvarial critical-size defect model (Izp-2024/1-0509) LICENSE:CC-BY-4.0 DOI: -28/03/2025

Type: Dataset

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

Data is being collected in order to confirm the purity of the synthesized materials needed for the creation of the biomaterial embedded microfluidic platform directly associated to the main objective of the Project.

Data origin is from the performed measurements using analytical instruments during the course of the Project's implementation.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Experimental data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

- XML
- TXT
- PDF
- CSV
- XLS

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

100

MB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

Yes, we have considered re-using of any existing data, however in our case it does not apply.

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

The data in this dataset might be useful to other researchers, e.g., material scientists, chemists, chemical engineers, biomedical engineers, biologists, computational chemists and computer modelling experts, as well as industry R&D specialists, and to anyone interested in calcium phosphate and biomaterial physicochemical property characterization and understanding.

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

No

Metadata will include measurement parameters of the data included in the dataset described in readme.txt text file.

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

restricted, request access (access is restricted, but request with collaboration proposal could be submitted to the authors)

Due to the potential of Intellectual Property protection data will not be made open, but with a restricted access upon reasonable request.

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

Yes

Comment:

Embargo period for data access will be set due to the possibility of creation of Intellectual Property worth protecting via patent application.

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org/>

Zenodo is one of the most popular repositories in Europe for any type of data. It is not restricted to specific datasets or fields. Project team already have experience of using it.

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

No special tools, generally available software capable of opening data file formats mentioned in 1.1.3.

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

The expected data formats are XML, TXT, PDF, CSV, XLS.

These data formats can be open using following softwares:

XML - any text editor,

TXT - any text editor,

PDF - any open source web browser, e.g., Firefox,

CSV - any text editor,

XLS - open-source suite that supports XLS spreadsheets, e.g., Apache OpenOffice Calc.

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial 4.0

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

2.4.3 When will the data be made available for re-use?

2028-06-30

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

No

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

WP3: Characterization of the developed bone-on-chip platform and comparison to in vivo experiments

This dataset will include all relevant data planned for publication under the framework of the Project's Work Package 3. Data within the Work Package 3 will be obtained from XRD, FT-IR, SEM, mass spectrometry, optical microscopy measurements.

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

Data is being collected in order to assess the complete bone-on-chip device comprising a microfluidic chip, bone-like biomaterials, and cells. Further, the data are being collected for the in vitro-in vivo correlation between the data obtained from bone-on-chip model and in vivo data from rat calvarial critical-size defect model

Data origin:

- 1) from the performed measurements using various analytical instruments during the course of the Project's implementation;
- 2) in vivo data from rat calvarial critical-size defect model will be re-used from another project (BBCE project, GA No 857287).

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Experimental data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

- XML
- TXT
- PDF
- CSV
- TIFF
- XLS

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

1

GB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

Yes

1.1.7 If Yes, please indicate what data set are you re-using?

id: null, Type: null

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

The data in this dataset might be useful to other researchers, e.g., material scientists, chemists, chemical engineers, biomedical engineers, biologists, computational chemists and computer modelling experts, as well as industry R&D specialists, and to anyone interested in calcium phosphate, biomaterial, in vitro model, microfluidics and metabolomics research and understanding.

2 Research Data Management

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2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

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DOI

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- CSV - any text editor,

- TIFF - open-source image editor that supports TIFF files, e.g., GIMP,
- XLS - open-source suite that supports XLS spreadsheets, e.g., Apache OpenOffice Calc.

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

Yes

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No

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Euro

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

WP1: Bone on a chip design and selection of chip materials

This dataset will include all relevant data planned for publication under the framework of the Project's Work Package 1.

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

[1 Data Summary](#)

[2 Research Data Management](#)

[3 Resources and Security](#)

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